

Mechanism of Oxidation of Thiocarbamides: 1-Benzylthiocarbamide

P. K. Srivastava and Y. Ramachandra Rao

Analogous to the oxidation of phenylthiocarbamide to Hector's base¹, the final product of oxidation of 1-benzylthiocarbamide has been shown to be 3-benzylimino-4-benzyl-5-imino-1,2,4-thiadiazolidine. In this oxidation the related bis-formamidine disulphide, monosulphide, and probably the 1-benzylformamidino-1-benzylthiocarbamide also are formed as intermediate stages. On reduction with ammoniacal hydrogen sulphide, the 3-benzylimino-4-benzyl-5-imino-1,2,4-thiadiazolidine affords, as expected, thiocyanic acid and the above related amidinothiocarbamide as principal products and small quantities of 1-benzylformamidino-3-benzylthiocarbamide which has been shown to arise by an isomeric change of 1-benzylformamidino-1-benzylthiocarbamide.

Heterocyclic bases²⁻⁶ are known to be formed by oxidation of 1-aryl-, 1,1- and 1,3-diaryl-, and alkylaryl-thiocarbamides. Depending on the conditions of the reaction, these have been found to be benzothiazole, thiadiazole or thiadiazolidine derivatives or other bases of yet undecided structure. For example, oxidation of 1-phenyl-, 1,3-diphenyl- and 1,3-methylphenyl-thiocarbamides with bromine in an indifferent solvent like chloroform or carbon tetrachloride afforded compounds of type A, whereas in ethanolic medium, B, C, and D respectively were obtained from 1-phenyl-, 1,3-diphenyl-, and 1,1-methylphenyl-thiocarbamides. Similar benzothiazole or thiadiazole derivatives were obtained from other substituted thiocarbamides as well.

(A)

(B)

(C)

(D)

(where R = Ph or Me or H)

1. Hector, *Ber.*, 1899, 22, 1179.
2. Hagershoff, *Ber.*, 1903, 36, 3131.
3. Hofmann and Gabriel, *Ber.*, 1892, 25, 1578.
4. Suresh, *J. Sci. Res., B.H.U.*, 1958-59, 9, No. 3, 64.
5. Verma and Sarkar, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1962, 21B, 236.
6. Joshua *et al.*, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1961, No. 10, p. 669.

The above compounds (A to D) represent final oxidation products which have been shown to be preceded by more than one intermediate stages⁷⁻⁹. For example, in the case of 1-methyl-3-phenylthiocarbamide⁹, related substituted bis-formamidine disulphide, monosulphide, amidinothiocarbamide, and isomeric 3-(substituted amidino) benzothiazole successively precede the formation of (C) (where the NPh and N'Ph are replaced by N-Me and N'-Me respectively).

No information is, however, available in the literature on the oxidation of alkyl-substituted thiocarbamides except that in a few cases related bis-substituted formamidine disulphide salts are known¹⁰ which are believed to decompose on further oxidation. To gain further insight into these, oxidation of 1-benzylthiocarbamide has now been investigated.

On oxidation with bromine or thionyl chloride in chloroform, bis-benzylformamidine disulphide dihydrobromide and dihydrochloride (I), respectively, which exhibited all the characteristic reactions of a bis-formamidine disulphide salt¹¹, were obtained. On careful treatment with ethanol, the disulphide dihydrobromide eliminated an atom of sulphur and afforded the dihydrobromide of a new base (II), found identical with the product synthesised from 1-benzylthiocarbamide and benzyl cyanamide in presence of hydrochloric acid and identified as bis-benzylformamidine monosulphide. The base (II) could not be further oxidised directly, but it decomposed like other similar monosulphides into benzylthiocarbamide, benzylcarbamide, and monobenzylguanidine. The ethanolic mother liquor, left behind after removing the base (II), when further treated with bromine followed by basification, afforded yet another base which, as judged from its properties (vide Experimental) and easy reduction to 1-benzylformamidino-1-benzylthiocarbamide and thiocyanic acid, appeared to be 3-benzylimino-4-benzyl-5-imino-1,2,4-thiadiazolidine (IV).

Since the thiadiazolidine (IV) is analogous to Hector's base¹, it is reasonable to assume that like the latter it must have been preceded in its formation by the amidinothiocarbamide (III) which can arise by migration of the benzylformamidino group from the sulphur to nitrogen in base (II)¹². That compound (III), as expected, is 1-benzylformamidino-1-benzylthiocarbamide is confirmed by synthesis of the only other possible isomer, the 1-benzylformamidino-3-benzylthiocarbamide (V) which is also formed by the action of ammonia on (III). On oxidation, product (V) afforded 3,5-dibenzylimino-1,2,4-thiadiazolidine (VI), analogous to the oxidation of 1-phenylformamidino-3-phenylthiocarbamide to 3,5-diphenylimino-1,2,4-thiadiazolidine¹³. The above reactions can be represented by the following scheme.

7. Sahasrabudhey and Nambury, *Proc. Indian Sci. Cong.*, 1958, Part III, p. 136.

8. Suresh, *this Journal*, 1960, **37**, 493.

9. Srivastava, *Indian J. Chem.* 1963, in press.

10. Sahasrabudhey and Singh, *this Journal*, 1952, **29**, 636; 1953, **30**, 449.

11. Werner, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, **101**, 2186, 2180.

12. Pandeya, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1963, **1**, 275.

13. Kurzer, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1958, 526; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 2345.

EXPERIMENTAL

(1). *Bis-(benzylformamidine)-disulphide Dihydrobromide* (I).—To finely powdered 1-benzylthiocarbamide (4 g.), suspended in chloroform (10 ml), a molar equivalent of bromine (1.5 ml), dissolved in chloroform (10 ml), was added gradually with cooling. The mixture was left overnight and the product washed with dry chloroform and acetone to remove excess of bromine and unchanged 1-benzylthiocarbamide. It was crystallised from HBr (dil.), m. p. 191–92°. (Found: C, 39.49; H, 4.43; N, 11.33; S, 13.53; equiv., 248.8. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_4\text{S}_2 \cdot 2\text{HBr}$ requires C, 39.02; H, 4.43; N, 11.4; S, 13.0%; equiv., 246). It liberated iodine from KI in absolute ethanolic solution and decomposed almost immediately, when treated with hot water, to elemental sulphur, benzylthiocarbamide, and benzylcarbamide.

(2). *Bis-(benzylformamidine)-monosulphide Dihydrobromide* (II).—The above disulphide salt (5 g.) was dissolved in ethanol and the solution left overnight. Elemental sulphur separating was filtered; to the filtrate acetone was added in excess and the precipitated product (0.8 g.) collected. It could not be crystallised without decomposition; m. p. 195–96°. (Found: N, 10.92; Br, 32.58; S, 6.32; equiv. 246.0. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_4\text{S} \cdot 2\text{HBr} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 11.11; Br, 32.24; S, 6.95%; equiv., 248). The mother liquor was treated further as in another experiment (*vide infra*). Its ethanolic solution furnished a picrate, m. p. 108–109°. On treatment with acidic ethanol or hot water it decomposed to benzyl-

thiocarbamide and benzylcarbamide. On oxidation with bromine in dilute ethanolic solution, the same decomposition products were obtained.

(3). *Bis-(benzylformamidino)-monosulphide Dihydrochloride*.—An intimate mixture of 1-benzylthiocarbamide (5 g.) and lead oxide (10 g.) was heated in acetone or ethanol (50 ml) under reflux on a water bath for about 30-40 minutes. Lead sulphide was filtered and through the clear filtrate HCl gas passed for about 5 minutes. Bis-(benzylformamidino)-monosulphide dihydrochloride was precipitated as white shining plates, m.p. 182-83°. It could not be crystallised without decomposition. (Found: C, 50.91; H, 5.70; N, 15.46; Cl, 19.76; S, 9.41; equiv., 177.6. $C_{16}H_{18}N_4S_2 \cdot 2HCl$ requires C, 51.75; H, 5.39; N, 15.10; Cl, 19.13; S, 8.62%; equiv., 185.5). Its ethanolic solution afforded a picrate, m.p. 108-109°. Its m.p. did not show any depression when admixed with the picrate of bis-(benzylformamidino)-monosulphide dihydrobromide (II) (*vide supra*).

(4). *3-Benzylimino-4-benzyl-5-imino-1,2,4-thiadiazolidine* (IV).—The mother liquor left behind after removal of the monosulphide salt as in Expt. 2, when further treated with dilute ethanolic bromine solution with cooling and stirring followed by basification with ammonia, afforded 1.5 g. of a new base. It crystallised from dilute ethanol, m.p. 142°. (Found: C, 65.04; H, 5.37; N, 18.91; S, 11.48. $C_6H_6N_4S$ requires C, 64.86; H, 5.40; N, 18.92; S, 10.80%). Its ethanolic solution provided a picrate, m.p. 153°.

The base on refluxing for a few minutes with ethanolic solution of phenyl isothiocyanate afforded a product which was crystallised from EtOH; m.p. 190°. (Found: N, 16.12. $C_6H_6N_4S$. C_6H_5NCS requires N, 16.22%). It also condensed with CS_2 on gentle warming in ethanolic medium, forming a pale yellow solid which was crystallised from the same solvent; m.p. 186°. (Found: N, 14.71. $C_6H_6N_4S \cdot CS_2$ requires N, 15.05%). It formed a *monoacetyl* derivative, m.p. 164°. (Found: N, 17.5. $C_6H_5N_4S \cdot COCH_3$ requires N, 16.57%). All these reactions are analogous to those of Hector's base¹⁴.

(5). *Reduction of 3-Benzylimino-4-benzyl-5-imino-1,2,4-thiadiazolidine* (IV) with *Ammoniacal Hydrogen Sulphide: Formation of 1-Benzylformamidino-1-benzylthiocarbamide* (III).—The base (IV, 1 g.), obtained in Expt. 4, was dissolved in ethanolic ammonia and through it H_2S passed for about 15 minutes. A colorless product separating was filtered. It was purified by dissolving in dilute acid and reprecipitation by basification. It could not be crystallised without decomposition; m.p. 112°. Its ethanolic solution afforded a picrate, m.p. 144°. (Found: C, 50.69; H, 3.86; N, 19.11. $C_6H_{16}N_4S \cdot C_6H_5N_3O$ requires C, 50.09; H, 4.49; N, 18.91%). On prolonged treatment of (IV) with warm ammoniacal H_2S , in addition to the above base, thiocyanic acid and dibenzylguanidine (m.p. 104°) were obtained. The base (III) (m.p. 112°) on oxidation with bromine in dilute ethanolic solution reformed the base (IV).

(6). *1-Benzylformamidino-3-benzylthiocarbamide* (V) and its *Oxidation to 3,5-Dibenzylimino-1,2,4-thiadiazolidine* (VI).—On prolonged boiling with ethanolic ammonia, compound (III) afforded a sticky product which from ethanolic solution provided a fluffy picrate, identified as the picrate of (V) (*vide infra*). It was crystallised from EtOH, m.p. 162°. (Found: C, 51.98; H, 4.49; N, 19.31. $C_{16}H_{18}N_4S \cdot C_6H_5N_3O$ requires C, 50.09; H, 4.49; N, 18.91%). The original sticky product on oxidation with bromine in dilute ethanolic

solution afforded a base, identified as 3,5-dibenzylimino-1,2,4-thiadiazolidine (VI); crystals from EtOH, m.p. 108° (*vide infra*).

1-Benzylformamidino-3-benzylthiocarbamide (V) was synthesised by condensing monobenzylguanidine with benzyl isothiocyanate¹⁵. It was crystallised from ethanol or methanol, m.p. 112°. (Found: C, 64.74; H, 5.69; N, 18.20. $C_{16}H_{16}N_4S$ requires C, 64.42; H, 6.04; N, 18.79%). *Picrate*, m.p. 162°. It did not show any depression in m.p. when admixed with the picrate described above. On oxidation with bromine in dilute ethanolic solution, it provided a new base which was crystallised for ethanol, m.p. 108°. (Found: C, 64.64; H, 5.58; N, 18.80. $C_{16}H_{16}N_4S$ requires C, 64.86; H, 5.40; N, 18.92%). It did not show any depression in m.p. when admixed with the product described above.

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ORGANIC CHEMISTRY RESEARCH SECTION,
CHEMISTRY DEPARTMENT,
BANARAS HINDU UNIVERSITY,
VARANASI-5.

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15. Cf. Dixit, Ph.D. Thesis, 1962, Banaras Hindu University.